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Modern Manifestations of Anxiety in Children of Preschool Age

Khasanova Saidahan Ganijonovna

Andijan State University Department of general psychology v.b. Associate Professor (PhD)

Abstract: in the preschool age period, children experience various emotional and psychological states. Anxiety, being in one of these cases, plays an important role in children's self-expression, social relationships and educational processes. In this article, we will talk about modern manifestations of anxiety in preschool children and measures to reduce them.

Key words: anxiety, preschool age, psychological development, social networks, technology, emotional support, stress, social environment, parents , healthy communication, social skills, effective strategies.

Introduction

Anxiety in children of preschool age is today a pressing problem in connection with social, economic and technological changes. This age group, that is, children between the ages of 3 and 7 years, experience a psychologically very delicate period. Their emotional states, development and social relationships are influenced by many factors.

In the conditions of modern life, children are faced with many sources of stress. The development of technology, the working conditions of parents and caregivers, the process of preparing for school, as well as changes in the social environment lead to an increase in children's anxiety levels. For children, concerns are manifested, in particular, as problems associated with adaptation to a new environment, interaction and self-expression.

This topic helps to deeply understand the psychology of children, educational environment and social activities. There is also the need to develop effective strategies to identify and reduce anxiety in children. Therefore, the study of modern manifestations of anxiety in children of preschool age remains an urgent issue.

Anxiety is the process by which a child prepares for psychologically or physiologically dangerous situations. This process can affect the psychological development and behavior of children. Modern research suggests that anxiety may be caused by a variety of factors in children's lives, including social, economic, and environmental conditions.

Modern manifestations of anxiety include:

Technology and anxiety - nowadays, children are quickly adapting to technology. Mobile phones, social networks and other digital platforms can increase social anxiety in children. There is a possibility that they have a negative impact on their relationship, sense of competition, and self-assessment.

Let's talk about technology and anxiety factors and solutions in children.

Use of social networks

When children are actively involved in social networks, they can feel competition and pressure among themselves. Constant comparisons about " success "or" visibility " increase anxiety.

Information redundancy

Having access to a large amount of information over the Internet can be a challenge for children. They may have difficulty filtering information, resulting in uncertainty and anxiety.

Self-requirements in preschool organizations

Children who receive education using online education and digital tools can put a high demand on themselves in mastering new technologies and knowledge, which increases stress and anxiety.

Social isolation

Long-term dependence on the phone or television screen reduces social isolation and interaction in children, which can lead to anxiety and depression States.

We looked at the factors of the emergence of anxiety States through modern technologies in children of pre-school age. That's now let's look at a number of solutions to them.

The role of parents and caregivers is to ensure that parents control their children's use of technology, as well as train them for responsible and balanced use. Talking to them openly about technology can help children with inappropriate or high anxiety.

Time restriction-it is important to limit the time spent by children on mobile phones or television, to encourage their involvement in other activities. Sports, art and creative activities improve children's emotional health.

Establishing healthy communication-encouraging children to express their feelings and allowing them to discuss their concerns, improves their emotional state. Parents and caregivers should listen to their children's feelings.

Educational programs and seminars - it is possible to organize seminars and educational programs for parents to effectively use technology and support the psychological health of children. This increases the knowledge of parents and provides an opportunity to better help their children.

Children's age-appropriate content-choosing suitable and useful content for children, improves their psychological health. Teachers and parents should recommend quality and developing games and programs for children.

So, technology can bring new factors of anxiety in children, but with the right approaches and support, this anxiety can be reduced. Together, parents, caregivers, and society are required to monitor and assist children in the proper use of technology. This contributes significantly to the healthy psychological development of children.

Parental influence in preschool child anxiety-parents can increase or decrease their children's anxiety. Their support, methods of discussing concerns directly affect the psychology of children. Parental stress and uncertainties can cause increased anxiety in children.

The social environment and activities at school - preparation for school, entering a new environment and finding a place in the group-increase anxiety in children. School stress, relationships with classmates, and contacts with teachers determine the level of anxiety.

As measures to reduce this anxiety, we recommend the following.

Emotional support-giving children the opportunity to express their feelings, listening to them and supporting them can reduce anxiety. Parents and caregivers are required to provide children with an environment conducive to expressing their concerns.

Social skills development-social skills development programs for preschool children are very important. Group activities, games and communication can help children reduce anxiety.

Self-control strategies - children should be taught simple ways to manage stress and reduce anxiety. For example, deep breathing, meditation, or soothing games can reduce anxiety.

So it is worth noting that in place of the conclusion. Anxiety in children of preschool age appears in modern living conditions, depending on many factors. Their influence in the social and technological environment, the role of parents, the process of preparing for school and many other factors affect the psychology of children. To reduce anxiety, children need emotional support, teaching stress management techniques, and developing social skills. Parents and caregivers play an important role in this process and should help children overcome anxiety.

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